

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part—XLIII. Syntheses of α -Anhydro-*O*-Trimethylbrazilone and α -Anhydro-*O*-Tetramethylhaematoxylone

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The compounds named in the title were secured by a modified (copper—catalysed) Cook-Schoental cyclisation of appropriate diazo-ketones.

IN an earlier communication¹ we have reported the copper catalysed cyclisation of 2-diazoacetyl-3-arylbenzo[b]furan leading to hydroxy γ -brazans (cf. Cook-Schoental cyclisation²). α -Anhydro-*O*-trimethylbrazilone (IX) and α -anhydro-*O*-tetramethylhaematoxylone (XI) have now been synthesised from the cyclisation of appropriate 2-diazoacetyl-3-arylbenzo[b]furan (IV) and (VIII) respectively, although reported attempts using sulphuric acid had failed (Johnson and Robertson³). Here again the use of copper-bronze in benzene led to success (*Vide* Experimental).

The intermediate 3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid⁴ (III) for the synthesis of (IX) was prepared by a different route. Thus the condensation of ω -bromoacetoveratrone with *m*-methoxyphenol in acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate afforded ω -(*m*-methoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone which on cyclodehydration gave 3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan (I). The latter was formylated with *N,N*-dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride to give the aldehyde (II) which on oxidation with alkaline silver nitrate afforded the acid (III).

- (I) $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$
 (II) $R_1 = H, R_2 = OCH_3, R_3 = CHO$
 (III) $R_1 = H, R_2 = OCH_3, R_3 = COOH$
 (IV) $R_1 = H, R_2 = OCH_3, R_3 = COCHN_2$
 (V) $R_1 = H, R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$
 (VI) $R_1 = CHO, R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$
 (VII) $R_1 = COOH, R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$
 (VIII) $R_1 = COCHN_2, R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$

- (IX) $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3$
 (X) $R_2 = H, R_3 = OCH_3, R_1 = OAc$
 (XI) $R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3, R_1 = H$
 (XII) $R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3, R_1 = OAc$

In the same way, ω -bromoacetoveratrone was condensed with 2,3-dimethoxyphenol leading to the ω -(2,3-dimethoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone which was cyclodehydrated and the resulting furan formylated and oxidised to the acid (VII).

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The IR spectra were determined in Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer, model—237.

*ω -(*m*-Methoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone*: A mixture of ω -bromoacetoveratrone (6.5 g), *m*-methoxyphenol (3.1 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 hours. The mixture was filtered, the solvent removed and the solid residue was triturated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. This was filtered, washed with water and dried, and crystallised from methanol to afford cream coloured crystals of *ω -(*m*-methoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone*, m.p. 90°. (Found: C, 67.39; H, 5.81. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5$ requires C, 67.54; H, 6.00%). ν_{max} 1685 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared and crystallised from ethyl acetate in brilliant red crystals, m.p. 177°. (Found: N, 11.68. $C_{25}H_{22}O_5N_4$ requires N, 11.61%).

3-(3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan (I): The foregoing ketone (5 g) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed with phosphorus pentoxide (25 g) for 10 hours. On working in the usual manner, the desired benzofuran was obtained as solid (4.25 g) which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colourless silky needles, m.p. 74-75° (lit⁸, m.p. 74°).

2-Formyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan (II): A mixture of the above benzofuran (4.3 g), N, N-dimethylformamide (0.7 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (2.1 ml) was heated on water bath for 10 hours at the end of which it was basified with 10% sodium hydroxide and again heated for one hour. The mixture was cooled, the solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol to give pale yellow needles (4.1 g), m.p. 158° of 2-formyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan, (lit⁸, m.p. 158°); (Found: C, 69.15; H, 5.08. Calculated for: C₁₈H₁₆O₅ C, 69.20; H, 5.10%). ν_{\max} 1668 cm⁻¹.

3-(3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxybenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic Acid (III): A mixture of the above aldehyde (1.8 g) and silver nitrate solution (12.8 ml; 8%) was refluxed and sodium hydroxide solution (3 ml; 15%) was added dropwise to it during half an hour. The refluxing was continued for 4 hours. The mixture was filtered and acidified to give the acid (1.2 g) which was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow prismatic crystals, m.p. 204-205° (decomp.) (lit⁸, m.p. 204°). (Found: C, 65.79; H, 5.10. Calculated for: C₁₈H₁₆O₆ C, 65.90; H, 4.90%). ν_{\max} 1678 cm⁻¹.

α -Anhydro-O-trimethylbrazilone (IX): The aforesaid acid (2 g) was suspended in dry benzene (15 ml) and refluxed for 2 hours with thionyl chloride (3 ml) and a drop of dry pyridine. After removing the solvent and excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure the acid chloride was obtained as a light green solid. Suspension of this acid chloride in dry ether was added dropwise to the cooled solution of excess of ethereal diazomethane (from 10 g nitrosomethylurea). The mixture was left overnight in the refrigerator. The crystalline diazoketone thus obtained after removal of the solvent under reduced pressure was crystallised from benzene light petroleum ether in yellow prisms (1.5 g), m.p. 159° (decomp.) (lit⁸, m.p. 159°); ν_{\max} 2120 cm⁻¹.

A solution of this diazoketone (IV) in dry benzene (25 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of copper-bronze powder (0.15 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) pre-heated at 55-60°. Heating and stirring was continued for 2 hours when evolution of nitrogen had ceased and then the mixture was filtered. The filtrate was extracted with 2% sodium hydroxide solution and the alkali extract was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and

then extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried (CaCl₂) and solvent was evaporated to give yellow solid of α -anhydro-O-trimethylbrazilone (IX) which crystallised from ethanol in yellow plates (0.25 g), m.p. 198-99° (lit⁸, m.p. 198°); ν_{\max} -OH absorptions at 3510 and 3395 cm⁻¹.

The alkaline solution of this phenol produced red dye with *p*-nitrobenzenediazonium chloride. The phenol also developed blue colour on warming with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution containing a drop of chloroform.

The acetate (X) prepared by the action of acetic anhydride in pyridine solution, crystallised from benzene in colourless clusters of needles, m.p. 175-76° (lit⁷, m.p. 174-75°); ν_{\max} 1765 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

ω -(2',3'-Dimethoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone: A mixture of ω -bromoacetoveratrone (7.8 g), 2,3-dimethoxyphenol (4.6 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.2 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 hours. On working up in the usual manner, ω -(2',3'-dimethoxyphenoxy)acetoveratrone was obtained as solid (7 g) which was crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 94-95°. (Found: C, 64.86; H, 6.16. C₁₈H₂₀O₆ requires C, 65.05; H, 6.07%); ν_{\max} 1687 cm⁻¹ (keto carbonyl).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared and crystallised from ethyl acetate in vermilion red crystals, m.p. 198-99°. (Found: N, 10.52. C₂₄H₂₄O₉N₄ requires N, 10.93%).

3-(3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-6,7-dimethoxybenzo[b]furan (V): The foregoing ketone (5 g) in dry benzene (75 ml) was refluxed with phosphorus pentoxide (25 g) for 12 hours. It was worked up in the usual manner to afford the benzofuran (V) (3.2 g) which was crystallised from benzene petroleum ether in cream-coloured crystals, m.p. 103-104°. (Found: C, 68.56; H, 5.68. C₁₈H₁₈O₅ requires C, 68.78; H, 5.77%).

2-Formyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6,7-dimethoxybenzo[b]furan (VI): A mixture of the above benzofuran (1.9 g), N, N-dimethylformamide (0.70 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (0.8 ml) was heated on water bath for 10 hours. On working up in the usual manner, 2-formyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6,7-dimethoxybenzo[b]furan (VI) (1.5 g) was obtained as solid. This crystallised from ethanol in colourless crystals, m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 66.34; H, 5.01. C₁₉H₁₈O₆ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.30%); ν_{\max} 1665 cm⁻¹ (aldehydic carbonyl).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate was obtained as vermilion red needles, m.p. 284-85° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.58. C₂₈H₂₂O₉N₄ requires N, 10.72%).

3-(3', 4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-6,7-dimethoxybenzo[b]-furan-2-carboxylic Acid(VII) : To a hot mixture of the above aldehyde (1.1 g) and silver nitrate solution (128 ml; 8%), sodium hydroxide solution (3 ml; 15%) was added dropwise and the refluxing was continued for 4 hours. The mixture was filtered, and acidified when 3-(3', 4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6,7-dimethoxybenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid(VII) (0.8 g) separated. It crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles, m.p. 229-30° (decom.) (lit⁴, m.p. 229-30°). (Found : C, 63.54; H, 5.16. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈O₇ : C, 63.68; H, 5.06%); ν_{\max} 1675 cm⁻¹.

α -Anhydro-O-tetramethylhaematoxylone(XI) : The above acid (2 g) was converted into the related diazomethylketone (1.7 g) by the method described earlier. The diazomethylketone was obtained as a yellowish brown crystalline solid, m.p. 156-57°; (ν_{\max} 2118 cm⁻¹). This diazoketone (0.5 g) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed with copper-bronze powder (50 mg) for 2 hours. An additional amount of copper-bronze powder (50 mg) was added to it and again refluxed for further 4 hours. Then the mixture was filtered, benzene was removed and the residue repeatedly extracted with 2% sodium hydroxide solution. The entire alkaline extract was acidified to give α -anhydro-O-tetramethylhaematoxylone (XI) as solid which was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates, m.p. 208-210° (lit^{4, 5, 6}, m.p. 202-206° and 208-10°). (Found : C, 67.85; H, 5.25. Calcd.

for C₂₀H₁₈O₆ : C, 67.79; H, 5.12%); ν_{\max} OH absorptions at 3510 and 3395 cm⁻¹.

On warming with a little alcoholic potassium hydroxide containing a drop of chloroform, the compound gave an intense bluish green colouration.

The acetate(XII) prepared by the action of acetic anhydride and pyridine was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in cream-coloured plate, m.p. 194° (lit⁶, m.p. 194°); ν_{\max} 1765 cm⁻¹(ester carbonyl).

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